

**A STUDY ON CUSTOMER SATISFACTION TOWARDS SERVICES
PROVIDED BY STATE BANK OF INDIA- WITH SPECIAL
REFERENCE TO NAGAPPATTINAM DISTRICT**

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ABSTRACT

Commercial banks play a significant role in helping the economy of a country in realizing its socio-economic goals. The role of commercial banking assumes much importance especially in a developing country like India. Customer satisfaction and service quality are inter-related. The higher the service quality the higher is the customer satisfaction may agree that in the banking sector, there are no recognized standard scales to measure the perceived quality of a bank service. Thus, competitive advantage through high quality service is an increasingly important weapon to survive- service quality has been found to be an important input to customer satisfaction. The banks are spending a lot of time and energy to frame policies about customer satisfaction.

Key words: Customers satisfaction, Banking services and service quality.

INTRODUCTION

Customer's satisfaction is measured at the individual level, but it is almost always reported at an aggregate level. Customer satisfaction, a term frequently used in marketing is a measure of how products and services supplied by a company meet or surpass customer expectation. Today customers are now becoming increasingly conscious of their right and are demanding ever more than before. The recent trends show that most of the banks are shifting from a 'product-centric model' to a Customer-centric model' since customer satisfaction has become are of the major

determination of business growth. The study will provide information about the satisfaction level of customers of SBI and banking sectors and will be help for framing new policies relating to the customers.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

In the current competitive world banks have to struggle their might to offer the best of the customer satisfaction through various innovative strategies in order to service in industry. Banking industry is passing through a challenging phase. The demonetization policy introduced by the government has affected the banking industry to a great extent. The banking sectors facing lot of challenges due to competition, technological developments, changing customer's needs and policies of government. In this competitive and fast changing era, it becomes imperative for a bank to satisfy the needs of the customers. The banks are spending a lot of time and energy to frame polices about customer satisfaction. The study would stand as a sincere attempt to evaluate customer satisfaction of SBI in Nagappattinam districts.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To examine the various services provided by SBI in Nagappattinam District.
2. To study the level of customer satisfaction towards the services provided by the SBI in the study area.
3. To examine the expectation and the level of satisfaction of the customer services rendered by state bank of India.
4. To suggest the strategies for the bank to improve the level of customer satisfaction.

METHODOLOGY

The study is based on primary and secondary data. The primary data were collected through a questionnaire and personal interview from the customer of the banks. The secondary data were collected from published text books, journals, reports and also online sources.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION OF DATA

Data were collected through primary sources and analyses with the help of simple percentage technique.

Table-1 Demographic variable

Demographic variables	No. of Respondents	Percentage
Sex		
Male	75	60
Female	50	40
Age		
Below 25 years	22	17.6
25 to 35 years	34	27.2
36 to 45 years	40	32.00
45 to 55 years	19	15.2
Above 55 years	10	8
Marital Status		
Married	83	66
Unmarried	42	34
Educational level		
Below HSC	27	21.6
Diploma	18	14.4
UG	38	30.4
PG	25	20
Above PG	17	13.6
Occupation		
Government	64	51.2
Private	24	19.2
Self-employee	16	12.8
Professional	13	10.4
Others	8	6.4
Monthly Income (Rs.)		
Upto 10,000	17	13.6
10,000 to 20,000	30	24
20,000 to 30,000	34	27.2
Above 30,000	44	35.2

Source: Primary Data

The above table shows about the demographic profile of the respondents were the sample was collected with 125 respondents who are customers of SBI in Nagai

district. In analyzing about the researcher have selected 60% of the respondents are male categories and 40% of them female categories. In analyzing about the age of the more respondents are from 35 to 45 years with 32%. A total 83 respondents were married which showed a (66%) and the unmarried 42 respondents accounted for 34%. In analyzing about educational level of the respondents, most of them which showed a 30.4% have completed their UG level. Among the occupational categories, 64 (51.2%) respondents were government servants. The income wise classification showed that the most of respondents i.e. 44 (35.2%) were in level of income above Rs.30, 000.

Table 2 Mode of dealing with bank

Dealing	No. of Respondents	Percentage
E- Banking	80	64
Traditional Banking	45	35

Source: Primary Data

Table 2 shows that, out of the total 125 respondents 64% opted the E- banking and 36% opted the traditional banking.

Table 3 Level of satisfaction of customers in over all services of bank

HS- Highly satisfied; S- Satisfied; N- Neutral, D-Dissatisfied and HD- Highly Dissatisfied

Banking Services	HS	%	S	%	N	%	D	%	H	%
ATM services	56	44.8	33	26.4	20	16	9	7.2	7	5.6
Internet Banking services	28	22.4	39	31.2	34	27.2	14	11.2	10	8
Telephone banking services	26	20.8	42	33.6	28	22.4	16	12.8	13	10.4
Mobile banking services	59	47.2	31	24.8	20	16	10	8	5	4
Traditional banking services	50	40	33	26.4	22	17.6	12	9.6	8	6.4

The above table shows about the level of satisfaction of customers towards over all services of bank. The ATM services of bank, most of the respondents represent were highly satisfied (44.8%), and about Internet banking services of the bank most of the respondents were satisfied (31.2%) and neutral (27.2%). The telephone services of the bank most of the respondents were satisfied (33.6%). The mobile and Traditional Banking services of the bank most of the respondents represent were highly satisfied 47.2% and 40% respectively.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

The survey has been conducted only on 125 respondents. The accuracy of the findings of study depends upon the correctness of the responses provided by the respondents. The results of the analysis depend on the quality of data provided by the customers of the bank. The study is conducted only in Nagappattinam district.

FINDINGS

1. The classification of customers on the basis of sex. The researcher have selected 60% of the respondents are male categories and 40% of the respondents are female categories.
2. It is seen from the above analysis more than half of the respondents are government employees.
3. Majority of the respondents have possessed in saving bank account holder of the bank.
4. Majority of the customers are feeling highly satisfied for opinion about the services of the bank to customers.
5. More than half of the customers are represents purpose of the transaction with the bank for credit of salary, cash deposit and availing loan from the bank.
6. Time spending for the bank based on each and every transaction of the customers. More than 1/3rd of the respondents represent time spending for bank transaction minimum 10 to 15 minutes.
7. More than 2/3rd of the respondents availing both agriculture loan and jewel loan.

8. Generally ATM services of SBI is satisfied and more than half of the respondents are represent to retain the customer for better services of SBI.

SUGGESTIONS

1. The banker should encourage and extended more number of loans to their customers.
2. State bank of India should open ATM centre in the necessary area of the study and also based on the demand and supply of money the banker put them in ATM centre.
3. The bank not only raises the deposits mobilization of saving bank account and also encourages the other types of bank account and also government come forward increase the interest rate for all deposits of bank.
4. The State bank of India should be come forward open adequate branches in rural areas in Nagappattinam district.
5. The banker may be open a separate customer care center into the bank for development of banker and customer relationship.

CONCLUSION

A customer is not just money in the cash register. He is a human being with feelings and deserves to be treated with respect. Delivering customer satisfaction is at the heart of modern marketing, which is a post-purchase judgment of the consumers. The banking business is becoming more and more complex as result of liberalization and globalizations. With aggressive marketing strategies for generating business opportunities, banks have developed innovative products, keeping in view the needs of different classes of individual customers. The main aim of the study was to assess the service quality of bank and its impact of customer satisfaction. The study also tried to test the relationship that exists between customer satisfaction and their loyalty. The respondents of the bank mostly focus on people factor for improving customer satisfaction while the banks are focus on modern banking services, to attract its customers.

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